

Supplementary Text

Systematic descriptions of conodont genera and species from Liu (1994)

The following systematic descriptions of conodont genera and species are translated and compiled from Liu (1994), Conodont biostratigraphy and cyclic stratigraphy in Fengshan Age of Dingjiatan, Xishan, Beijing, an unpublished Master's thesis completed at Peking University, Beijing. These descriptions are provided to document the taxonomic provenance of the conodont biostratigraphic framework used for the Xiaweidian–Dingjiatan area. Meng Wang translated the original Chinese text and reorganized the descriptions for inclusion in this Supplementary Information. No new taxonomic revision is proposed here; these descriptions are included solely to make the previously published biostratigraphic framework more accessible and reproducible.

Genus *Cambrooistodus* Miller, 1980

Type species: *Oistodus cambricus* Miller, 1969

***Cambrooistodus minutus* Miller, 1980**

(Plate I, fig. 7)

Oistodus minutus Miller part, 1969, p. 433, text-fig. 5B, pl. 66, figs. 1–4.

Cambrooistodus minutus Miller, 1980, p. 11, text-fig. 4F, pl. 1, fig. 8; An, 1982, p. 129, pl. 11, figs. 15–16, pl. 15, fig. 10; Chen et al., 1986, p. 122, pl. 32, fig. 16.

Description: Simple coniform element, erect to recurved. The main cusp is composed of white matter and is laterally compressed, with distinct anterior and posterior marginal ridges. A prominent posterior process forms an acute angle with the posterior ridge. The basal cavity is very shallow, with its apex reaching only the height of the posterior process. The element is asymmetrical owing to lateral curvature of the cusp.

Stratigraphic occurrence. Middle Fengshan Formation, Dingjiatan. *Cambrooistodus minutus* Subzone.

Genus *Cordylodus* Pander, 1856

Type species: *Cordylodus angulatus* Pander, 1856.

***Cordylodus proavus* Mueller, 1959**

(Plate II, figs. 15 and 16)

Cordylodus proavus Mueller, 1959, p. 448, text-fig. 3B, pl. 15, figs. 11, 12, 18; Miller, 1969, p. 424, text-fig. 3D, pl. 65, figs. 37–45; Druce and Jones part, 1971, p. 70, not text-fig. 23p, pl. 1, figs. 2–6, not fig. 1; Miller, 1980, pp. 19–20, text-figs. 4G, H, pl. 1, figs. 14, 15; An, 1982, pp. 129–130, pl. 16, figs. 1–4, 6, pl. 17, figs. 10–13; An et al., 1983, pp. 87–88, pl. 7, figs. 1–5, 8, 11; Dong, 1984, pp. 395–396, pl. 1, figs. 1, 2; Chen et al., 1986, pp. 130–133, text-fig. 40, pl. 35, figs. 1, 4–5, 7–8, 10–14, pl. 36, figs. 1–6, 8–24, pl. 37, figs. 9, 12, 14, pl. 38, figs. 1, 4, 6, 9, 11–12, 14, 16–18.

Cordylodus cf. *C. proavus* Druce and Jones, 1971, p. 71, text-fig. 23s, pl. 1, figs. 10, 12.

Cordylodus oklahomensis Mueller, 1959, p. 447, text-fig. 3A, pl. 15, figs. 15, 16; Miller,

1969, p. 423, text-fig. 31, pl. 65, figs. 46–53.

Cordylodus aff. *C. proavus* An et al., 1983, p. 88, pl. 7, figs. 6, 7, 9, 10, text-fig. 10(3).

Description: Apparatus composed of two element types, including rounded and compressed elements. The basal cavity is large; the anterior slope is parallel to the anterior margin of the element. The basal cavity is deep and extends into the upper part of the element.

Rounded elements are symmetrical or slightly asymmetrical. The main cusp and denticles are circular to elliptical in transverse section. Denticles number from one to six, are discrete from one another, and the aboral margin is flat or arched. The basal cavity may be elongate or short.

Compressed elements are asymmetrical. The main cusp and denticles are laterally compressed, and the main cusp commonly twists inward. The basal cavity extends posteriorly to form a distinct posterior process. The anterior and posterior margins of both the main cusp and denticles are sharp. The basal cavity is large, and the inner side near the base commonly bears a rib. Denticles number three to six, are fused basally, and become separated upward.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Middle to upper Fengshan Formation, *Cordylodus proavus* Zone to Lower Ordovician.

Cordylodus lindstromi Druce and Jones, 1971

(Plate II, figs. 17 and 18)

Cordylodus lindstromi Druce and Jones, 1971, p. 68, pl. 1, figs. 7–9, text-fig. 23b, pl. 2, fig. 8; An et al., 1983, p. 86, pl. 7, figs. 17–19; Chen et al., 1986, pp. 129–130, pl. 34, figs. 1, 5–8, text-fig. 39.

Description: Compound conodont. The main cusp reclines posteriorly and is biconvex laterally. The anterior and posterior ridges are relatively blunt. The basal part is generally large. The posterior basal region extends posteriorly to form a posterior process bearing one to five denticles. Denticles are biconvex, fused basally and separated upward.

Remarks: Mueller (1973) questioned the taxonomic significance of *C. lindstromi*, noting that specimens with basal-cavity morphologies comparable to those of *C. proavus*, *C. angulatus* and *C. intermedius* may also possess a secondary basal cavity. Chen et al. (1986), however, considered that the basal cavity of *C. lindstromi* in the lower part of the *C. lindstromi* Zone differs from that of *C. proavus*. In our material, *C. lindstromi* is regarded as a valid species, although the morphology of the secondary basal cavity is difficult to distinguish and its evolutionary relationship with *C. proavus* is difficult to assess. It is therefore inappropriate to use this character as the diagnostic element for defining a system boundary. In this paper we follow An (1983) and use the *Monocostodus sevierensis*–*Utahconus beimadaoensis* interval as the boundary criterion.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Lower Ordovician.

Genus *Coelocerodontus* Ethington, 1959

Type species: *Coelocerodontus trigonius* Ethington, 1959.

Generic diagnosis: Simple, hollow, angular coniform element. Lateral walls are thin and enclose a central cavity extending to the apex of the spine. The marginal ridge of the spine is keel-like. The outer surface is undulose, whereas the inner surface is flat.

***Coelocerodontus simplex* sp. nov.**

(Plate II, figs. 4 and 5)

Etymology: From Latin *simplex*, meaning simple.

Holotype: Middle Fengshan Formation, Beijing, Plate II, Fig. 5; collection number Df243; registration number BD94027.

Description: Element angular, simple and hollow. Outer wall thin; basal cavity deep and large, occupying the entire element. The element is simple and reclined posteriorly, asymmetrical laterally, with a flat and narrow inner side and a broader, more convex outer side. It is enrolled inward, causing the two lateral ridges to curve onto the inner surface. The outer wall is very thin and bears parallel ornamentation.

Remarks: The specimen is assigned to this genus on the basis of its simple and hollow element morphology, keel-like marginal ridge and thin outer wall. However, the present material is simpler than the type species and has fewer marginal ridges. These differences are clear, and a new species is therefore erected.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Middle Fengshan Formation, *C. proavus* Zone to Lower Ordovician.

Material: Six complete specimens.

Genus *Eoconodontus* Miller, 1980

Type species: *Proconodontus notchpeakensis* Miller, 1969.

***Eoconodontus notchpeakensis* Miller, 1980**

(Plate I, fig. 16)

Proconodontus notchpeakensis Miller, 1969, p. 438, text-fig. 5G, pl. 66, figs. 21–29; An et al., 1983, part, pp. 127–128, pl. 5, figs. 10–11, 12, not figs. 19, 20; An, 1982, p. 142, pl. 8, fig. 2, pl. 13, figs. 1–11.

Eoconodontus notchpeakensis Miller, 1980, pp. 22–23, pl. 1, figs. 10–12, text-figs. 3D, E; Dong, 1984, p. 399, pl. 1, figs. 3, 4, text-figs. 1C–D; Chen et al., 1986, pp. 140–141, pl. 19, fig. 13, pl. 31, figs. 2, 6, 8, pl. 32, figs. 2, 4, 6–7, not fig. 9, 11, p. 133, figs. 2, 8, text-fig. 48.

Description: Erect to posteriorly reclined simple coniform element, including compressed and rounded element types. The basal cavity varies considerably, being shallow or deep, and the cusp is correspondingly long or short. The cusp is smooth and composed of white matter. Rounded elements have an elliptical transverse section and are symmetrical or nearly symmetrical; anterior and posterior ridges may be present or absent. Compressed elements are laterally flattened, with sharp anterior and posterior ridges. They are asymmetrical owing to lateral inclination of the cusp, and the inner side commonly bears a ridge.

Stratigraphic occurrence. Fengshan Formation, *Eoconodontus notchpeakensis* Subzone to Lower Ordovician.

***Eoconodontus intermediacostus* sp. nov.**

(Plate I, fig. 5)

Eoconodontus notchpeakensis part, Chen et al., 1986, pl. 32, fig. 9.

Etymology: From Latin *intermedia*, middle, and *costus*, ridge.

Holotype: Fengshan Formation; collection number Df231; registration number BD94005.

Description: Nearly erect simple coniform element. The upper part of the cusp reclines posteriorly. The element is compressed anteriorly and posteriorly, with sharp marginal ridges. The cusp consists of white matter and is nearly bilaterally symmetrical. The basal cavity reaches the point of maximum curvature of the cusp. Both the inner and outer sides of the basal cavity bear a ridge extending from the basal margin to near the apex of the basal cavity, giving the transverse section of the basal cavity a concave quadrangular outline.

Remarks: Specimens with inner and outer ridges are consistent with *Eoconodontus* in element morphology and in the distribution of white matter. They differ from *E. notchpeakensis* in having distinct ridges on the inner and outer sides of the basal cavity, which give the basal cavity a quadrangular transverse section.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Fengshan Formation, *Eoconodontus notchpeakensis* Subzone.

Material: One nearly complete specimen.

Genus *Monocostodus* Miller, 1980

Type species. *Acodus sevierensis* Miller, 1969.

***Monocostodus sevierensis* Miller, 1969**

(Plate I, fig. 6)

Acodus sevierensis Miller, 1969, p. 418, pl. 63, figs. 25–31.

Acontiodus (Semiacontiodus) uncinostatus Miller, 1969, p. 421, pl. 64, figs. 49–54.

Drepanodus simplex Druce and Jones, 1971, p. 24, pl. 13, figs. 1–4.

Monocostodus sevierensis Miller, 1980, p. 27, pl. 2, figs. 8–9; An et al., 1983, p. 108, pl. 6, figs. 19–23; Chen et al., 1986, p. 152, pl. 43, figs. 19–22, text-fig. 56.

Description. Element bilaterally symmetrical or slightly asymmetrical. The cusp reclines posteriorly, bends strongly backward at its junction with the base, and then extends straight. The cusp is lenticular in transverse section. The anterior and posterior marginal ridges are sharp and become blade-like in the upper part because they thin upward. The basal cavity is shallow and triangular.

Remarks. We follow An (1983) in considering *Teridontus* and *Monocostodus* to be phylogenetically related. *Monocostodus sevierensis* is morphologically simple, possesses distinctive characters, is readily recognizable, and occurs at a relatively stable stratigraphic level worldwide. We therefore agree with An (1983) in using its lower boundary as the criterion for the Cambrian–Ordovician boundary.

Stratigraphic occurrence. Lower Ordovician.

Genus *Proacodus* Mueller, 1959

Type species: *Proacodus obliquus* Mueller, 1959.

Generic diagnosis: Simple, asymmetrical conodont element with a very large basal cavity. The anterior and posterior margins are rounded and lack ornamentation. The element bears a more or less broad, elongate costa.

***Proacodus tricostatus* sp. nov.**

(Plate I, fig. 22)

Etymology: From Latin *tri*, prefix meaning three, and *costatus*, ribbed or ridged.

Holotype: Fengshan Formation, Beijing; collection number Df231; registration number BD94022.

Description: Simple, slightly asymmetrical element. The cusp is subcircular and compressed; the posterior margin is ridged, and the anterior margin is relatively broad. A long anterior margin expands outward in a triangular form. The outer side bears two moderately developed marginal ridges, which merge at the base of the cusp to form a single anterior ridge. The basal cavity is large, with its apex reaching only the base of the cusp.

Remarks: The new species has an elongate anterior margin, resembling that of the type species. It differs, however, in that the elongate anterior margin of the new species is a plane surface, whereas that of the type species is a ridge. This distinction is clear. Although the upper part of the cusp is broken in the present specimen and no further diagnostic characters are preserved, the elongate anterior margin occurs only in *Proacodus*, and the specimen is therefore assigned to this genus.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Middle Fengshan Formation, *Cambroistodus minutus* Subzone.

Material: One specimen.

Genus *Proconodontus* Miller, 1969

Type species: *Proconodontus muelleri* Miller, 1969.

***Proconodontus antacostatus* sp. nov.**

(Plate I, fig. 1)

Etymology: From Latin *anta*, prefix meaning anterior, and *costatus*, ribbed or ridged.

Holotype: Basal Fengshan Formation, Beijing; collection number Df209; registration number BD94001.

Description: Element large and simple, erect to posteriorly reclined, laterally compressed, symmetrical or slightly asymmetrical. The posterior margin is narrowly rounded and lacks a distinct ridge. The anterior margin bears a prominent ridge extending from the base to the apex. The basal cavity is deep and reaches the apex of the element.

Remarks: The new species differs markedly from known species of *Proconodontus* in the development of the marginal ridge. Because marginal-ridge development is an important taxonomic character in this genus, the specimens bearing only an anterior ridge are assigned here to a new species. It may represent an anterior-ridged precursor element of *P. muelleri*, analogous to the posterior-ridged *P. posterocostatus*.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Basal Fengshan Formation.

Material: Ten specimens.

***Proconodontus muelleri* Miller, 1969**

(Plate I, fig. 2)

Proconodontus muelleri muelleri Miller, 1969, p. 437, text-fig. 5H, pl. 66, figs. 30–40.

Coelocerodontus burkei Druce and Jones part, 1971, p. 61, text-fig. 22A, not text-fig. 22E, pl. 11, figs. 9–11, not figs. 5–8, 12.

Proconodontus muelleri Miller, 1980, p. 29, text-fig. 4C, pl. 1, fig. 7; An part, 1982, pp. 141–142, pl. 12, figs. 8, 9, 11–13, pl. 16, fig. 10, not fig. 12; An et al. part, 1983, pp. 126–127, pl.

5, fig. 21; Chen et al., 1986, pp. 159–161, pl. 19, fig. 6, pl. 32, figs. 1, 3, 10, 12–14, 17, pl. 33, figs. 3–5, 11, text-fig. 60.

Description: Simple coniform element. The element is moderately laterally compressed and slightly posteriorly curved. It is commonly dark grey and opaque. Both anterior and posterior marginal ridges are developed. The element wall is relatively thick, and transverse growth lines are commonly visible on the wall. The basal cavity is deep and large, extending to the apex.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Middle to upper Fengshan Formation, from the *P. muelleri* Subzone to the *C. proavus* Zone.

***Proconodontus posterocostatus* Miller, 1980**

(Plate I, fig. 3)

Coelocerodontus burkei Druce and Jones part, 1971, p. 61, pl. 11, figs. 7, 8, not figs. 5, 6, 9–12.

Proconodontus posterocostatus Miller, 1980, pp. 30–31, text-fig. 4B, pl. 1, figs. 4–6; Chen et al., 1986, pl. 19, fig. 16, pl. 25, figs. 1, 6, 14, pl. 30, figs. 1, 3–4, 8–13, pl. 32, fig. 8, pl. 33, figs. 7, 9, text-fig. 61.

Description: Medium to large simple cone, erect to posteriorly reclined and symmetrical. Transverse section circular to elliptical. The basal cavity extends to the apex of the cusp. A distinct posterior ridge is present, but it commonly does not reach the basal margin. No anterior ridge is present.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Basal Fengshan Formation, *P. posterocostatus* Subzone.

Genus *Rotundonconus* An and Zhang, 1983

Type species: *Rotundonconus jingxiensis* An and Zhang in An et al., 1983.

Plate I, figs. 20, 21; Plate II, figs. 1–3, 6–8, 10, 11.

Remarks: Chen et al. (1986) considered that the surface of the elements of this genus bears granular ornamentation. The type specimens of An and Zhang (1983) also show granular ornamentation. In the present material, granular ornamentation is also common and is especially conspicuous on the ridges. We consider this genus to be phylogenetically related to *Hirsutodontus ani*. Chen et al. (1986) defined *R. cambrica* as an apparatus species composed of five elements. In our material, the five elements occur at the same stratigraphic level, and we therefore follow Chen's interpretation.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Fengshan Formation, *Proconodontus* Zone.

Gen. et sp. indet

(Plate II, fig. 9)

Description: Simple coniform element. The element resembles *Proconodontus* in morphology, is evenly posteriorly reclined, and is asymmetrical because the cusp twists inward. The anterior margin is ridged. The posterior margin divides into two ridges at the point of maximum curvature of the element, and these extend to the basal margin. The surface between the two ridges is V-shaped and concave. The element surface is smooth.

Remarks: This form differs from known Cambrian conodonts in having a posterior ridge that bifurcates into two ridges on the lower part of the element. Because only limited material is available, it is left unnamed here.

Stratigraphic occurrence: Upper part of the *Cambroistodus minutus* Subzone, Fengshan Formation.

Material: One specimen.

Plate I

1. *Proconodontus antacostatus* sp. nov.
Lateral view, $\times 100$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df209;
Registration number BD94001.
2. *P. muelleri* Miller
Lateral view, $\times 50$; horizon, lower Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df210;
Registration number BD94002.
3. *P. posterocostatus* Miller
Lateral view, $\times 100$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df209;
Registration number BD94003.
4. *P. serratus* Miller
Lateral view, $\times 60$; horizon, lower Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df216;
Registration number BD94004.
5. *Eoconodontus notchpeakensis* (Miller)
Lateral view, $\times 150$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df231;
Registration number BD94005.
6. *Monocostodus sevierensis* (Miller)
Lateral view, $\times 100$; horizon, upper Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df240;
Registration number BD94006.
7. *Cambroistodus minutus* (Miller)
Lateral view, $\times 120$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df228;
Registration number BD94007.
8. *C. cambricus* (Miller)
Lateral view, $\times 180$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df231;
Registration number BD94008.
9. *Bengtsonella triangularis* Mueller
Posterior view, $\times 170$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df208;
Registration number BD94009.
10. *Teridontus reclinatus* Jiang et Xiang
Lateral view, $\times 120$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df225;
Registration number BD94010.
11. *T. nakamurai* (Nogami)
Posterior view, $\times 100$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df209;
Registration number BD94011.
12. *Prooneotodus rotundatus* (Druce and Jones)
Lateral view, $\times 120$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df204;
Registration number BD94012.
13. *Drepanodus* sp. A.
Lateral view, $\times 150$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df231;
Registration number BD94013.

14. *D. sp. B*
Lateral view, $\times 170$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df231;
Registration number BD94014.
15. *D. sp. C*
Lateral view, $\times 150$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df236;
Registration number BD94015.
16. *Eoconodontus notchpeakensis* (Miller)
Lateral view, $\times 120$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df227;
Registration number BD94016.
17. *Prooneotodus gallatini* Mueller
Lateral view, $\times 100$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df209;
Registration number BD94017.
18. *Teridontus nakamurai nodus* Zhang H. J. et Xiang
Lateral view, $\times 100$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number Df209;
Registration number BD94018.
19. *Hirsutodontus ani* Wang
Posterolateral view, $\times 120$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number
Df206-2; Registration number BD94019.
- 20, 21. *Rotundonconus cambricus* (Nogami)
Lateral views, $\times 100$ and $\times 100$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number
Df206-2; Registration numbers BD94020 and BD94021.
22. *Proacodus tricostatus* sp. nov.
Latero-apical view, $\times 120$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number
Df231; Registration number BD94022.

Plate II

- 1–3, 8. *Rotundonconus cambricus* (Nogami)
1 and 3, posterior views, $\times 200$ and $\times 100$; 2 and 8, lateral views, $\times 120$; horizon, lower
Fengshan Formation. Collection numbers: 1, Df212; 2, Df206-2; 3, Df209; 8, Df216;
Registration numbers: 1, BD94023; 2, BD94024; 3, BD94025; 8, BD94030.
- 4, 5. *Coelocerodontus simplex* sp. nov.
4, posterior view, $\times 150$; 5, anterior view, $\times 150$; horizon, upper Fengshan Formation;
Collection number: Df243; Registration numbers: BD94026 and BD94027.
- 6, 11. *R. tricarinatus* (Nogami)
6, lateral view, $\times 130$; 11, posterior view, $\times 100$; horizon, lower Fengshan Formation;
Collection numbers: Df212 and Df208; Registration numbers: BD94028 and BD94033.
- 7, 10. *R. jingxiensis* (Nogami)
7, posterior view, $\times 120$; 10, posterior view, $\times 100$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation;
Collection number: Df208; Registration numbers: BD94029 and BD94032.
9. Gen. et sp. indet.
Lateral view, $\times 150$; horizon, upper Fengshan Formation; Collection number: Df231;
Registration number: BD94031.
12. *Prosagittodontus dahlmani* (Mueller)
Posterior view, $\times 150$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number: Df208;

Registration number: BD94034.

13. *Furnishina quadrata* Mueller

Posterior view, $\times 150$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number: Df208;

Registration number: BD94035.

14. *Furnishina aff. gludiata* Mueller

Posterior view, $\times 120$; horizon, basal Fengshan Formation; Collection number: Df204;

Registration number: BD94036.

15, 16. *Cordylodus proavus* Mueller.

Lateral views, $\times 100$ and $\times 100$; horizon, middle Fengshan Formation; Collection number: Df231; Registration numbers: BD94037 and BD94038.

17, 18. *Cordylodus lindstromi* Druce and Jones

Lateral views, $\times 200$ and $\times 200$; horizon, upper Fengshan Formation; Collection numbers: Df243 and Df240; Registration numbers: BD94039 and BD94040.

Supplementary References

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